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Work Package 10

Secure Infrastructure for big data

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Executive Summary

This report builds on the D10.2 deliverable of HEAP, which was focused on *Documentation of the secure platform and its integration into HEAP* and illustrates the final implemented system regarding the security measures that ensure the privacy and integrity of the data.

The report describes the data flow and where and how the data is stored. It also explains how researchers can authorise themselves to access the data, process it, and obtain the processing results, as well as details on protocols and specific security measures.

This report records the implementation efforts coordinated within the Secure infrastructure for sensitive data (WP10) and its goal to develop an IaaS (Infrastructure as a Service) platform for the HEAP Information Commons for storing and managing sensitive data as well as enabling the analysis of such data with the Hopsworks software (WP6) SaaS (Software as a Service).

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1 Introduction

1.1 Purpose

The activities of Work Package 10 focused mainly on implementing an IaaS (Infrastructure as a Service) secure data platform suitable for managing sensitive data.

As WP10 continued the work plan established in the D10.1 and D10.2 documents, the final structure has been simplified and streamlined, relying less on the CSC's SD Services suite of tools.

1.2 Overview

This report presents the results of the work that has been produced from the following tasks:

- Task 10.2 Development of sensitive data management platform
- Task 10.3 Dataset authorisation and access
- Task 10.4 Secure data access from institutional repositories
- Task 10.5 Support research use cases

A plan was first established for integrating Hopsworks software (Knowledge Engine, WP6) with the secure infrastructure mentioned in the D6.1 deliverable (Task 10.2). As a result of continuous collaboration, a new integration endpoint was identified through CSC Data Gateway software, which was provided as a means for secure access to data stored in SD Connect (Task 10.3).

1.3 Structure of the Document

- Chapter 1 - (this chapter) introduces the document and its purpose concerning the HEAP project.
- Chapter 2 - introduces ePouta and cPouta IaaS, Allas object storage service, and the CSC Sensitive Data Connect reused as part of the Human Exposome Assessment Platform.
- Chapter 3 explains the final design structure and the different use case flows.
- Chapter 4 - the risks and corresponding security measures are detailed.
- Chapter 5 - provides a summary of the key elements from this document.

2 Overview of ePouta and CSC Sensitive Data Connect

2.1 CSC ePouta Secure Cloud Infrastructure

ePouta [2] represents a cloud computing environment for processing sensitive data. It is designed as a closed environment (virtual private cloud) to meet elevated information security level regulations, suitable for all fields of science, government and research-sector organisations.

The ePouta cloud service is easily scalable to customers' requirements [3] and can be used to analyse sensitive data which requires large amounts of memory, processing power and/or clustered I/O performance.

The service is an IaaS (Infrastructure as a Service) cloud computing service, and it is part of the suite of solutions developed at CSC [1] to aid researchers in analysing sensitive data. It allows users to provision virtual machines and storage resources directly to their internal networks. The virtualised infrastructure consists of, but is not necessarily limited to, these resources:

- Virtual machines (instances).
- Block devices that can be attached to virtual machines (volumes).
- Virtual networks that can be used to connect virtual machines.

At its core, ePouta is based on the open-source cloud software OpenStack.

2.2 CSC cPouta General Cloud Infrastructure

cPouta is CSC's general-purpose cloud computing environment, equivalent to ePouta. It is designed to cover the use cases that do not require sensitive data protection.

The *cPouta* service offers the same kind of resources as ePouta (see above), and its core is also based on open-source cloud software OpenStack [4]. One of the main distinctions is the networking setup. *cPouta* offers publicly routed IPs called *Floating IPs*. While firewall protections can also be applied, *cPouta* allows connections to virtual machines directly from the Internet.

2.3 CSC Allas object storage service

Allas object storage is CSC's data pool storage service [5]. It allows researchers to store large quantities of data. The data submission and retrieval can be performed through several interfaces, such as:

- S3 API [6];
- OpenStack Swift [7];
- Web GUI at <https://allas.csc.fi>.

Any file type can be stored in Allas. Data is organised into "buckets", each bucket has to have a unique name for the whole Allas system. Inside a

bucket, normal files and folders can be stored; they do not require unique names, as the namespace of names is independent of other buckets. Following the S3 and Swift protocols, access is managed by a pair of Access and Secret keys. A given pair of Access and Secret keys provides read and write access to a set of buckets. This means that it is impossible to create read-only credentials or partial access to a bucket.

2.4 CSC Sensitive Data Connect

SD Connect [8] is intended to collect and store sensitive research data during the active phase of a research project. Built on top of the CSC object storage service (Allas [9]), it provides a user interface for submitting encrypted data and sharing data with other researchers, in the same or different projects, in the secure computing environment through SD Desktop. Data is encrypted using the Crypt4gh algorithm [10]. The data is encrypted at the origin, i.e., on the researcher's computer. It provides the same interfaces as *Allas* with the addition of:

- Web GUI at <https://sd-heap.rahtiapp.fi/>

All the data stored and processed in SD Services and ePouta is located in Finland. This instance of SD Connect is a dedicated instance, deployed for HEAP.

3 Final design structure

The final infrastructure uses Allas, ePouta, cPouta and Sensitive Data Connect. Sensitive Data Connect is a web interface that encrypts and submits data. Allas is used to store the encrypted data. cPouta is used as a secure gateway between the Internet and ePouta. And finally, ePouta is used to analyse the data. It differs from the previous plans for integrating with the CSC Sensitive Data Services suite of tools. The reason for this change was twofold: first, the departure of a key person in the Work Package shifted the team's knowledge out of Sensitive Data Services. Secondly, given that a redesign was deemed necessary, a simpler and more streamlined design was decided.

There are 2 different user interaction flows with the system, 1 system update flow, and 1 administrator interaction flow. See below a graph with the overall design of the system and the 4 different use cases:

The graph shows two different actors, the researcher on the top and the administrator on the bottom. Two networks are represented by two clouds: the general public Internet network on the top, and the CSC Internal Network. cPouta is on the left, ePouta in the center, and Allas and SD Connect on the right. A green tick represents open access, and a red cross represents closed access; both are labelled with the corresponding network protocol. Arrows show the direction of the flow of the information, and are labelled with the protocol used. Another notable element in the schema is

the data repository in Allas, represented by a cylinder. The two virtual machines are in cPouta, and the other is in ePouta, which act as proxies. And finally, the HopsWorks [20] cluster running on ePouta.

3.1 Data submission flow

This data flow is initiated by the researcher who wishes to submit and store data on the cluster.

The researcher first needs a CSC account. Once the CSC account has been obtained, the researcher will log into SD Connect. The communication uses only HTTPs connections that use Transport Layer Security (TLS) version 1.2 or better, secured with certificates issued by universally recognised Certificate Authorities and always within their validity period. The web application SD Connect will check and list the CSC projects in which the researcher is a member. Once the researcher chooses a project and a folder for that project, the upload process can start. The upload from the researcher's point of view is simple: use the web interface to select the files to upload, and provide a public Crypt4gh public key. CSC provides the public Crypt4gh key, meaning only CSC, who possess the private Crypt4gh key, can read the encrypted data. The data will be encrypted by the web interface on origin, i.e. in the researcher's computer. Once encrypted, the data will be copied using the HTTPs protocol that uses TLS, into SD Connect and from there into Allas using the Swift protocol. The data will remain encrypted at rest. For an attacker to retrieve the data, the private key and access to the private Allas project will be necessary.

3.2 Data analysis flow

The data analysis workflow is initiated by the researcher, in this case, when an analysis of the submitted data is required.

The researcher will use the Hopsworks application and needs a CSC account to log in. The process after authentication is transparent for the researcher. From the data flow point of view, the data is made accessible to the researcher by the S3 protocol [6] and a Filesystem in Userspace (FUSE) mount [12], which transparently streams and decrypts the data into a local folder inside HopsWorks. Data is only cached in the destination Virtual machine. The data is listed as available for analysis on the researcher's side. All researcher interaction is done via HTTPS in a web browser.

3.3 System update flow

The system update flow is triggered when new software versions are needed in any of the Virtual Machine hosts in ePouta.

The update process will use two chained HTTP Squid proxies, one on ePouta and the second in cPouta. The update process can be triggered by the distribution package manager "apt" [13] or by Python's package installer "pip" [14]. Both are instructed to contact the ePouta internal HTTP Proxy;

this proxy is configured with a whitelist of servers that correspond with the remote repositories of the aforementioned package managers. The first ePouta internal proxy will contact the second internal proxy, located in cPouta. Firewall rules are deployed to only allow proxy traffic. The firewall rules are deployed on the cloud management system (OpenStack Security Groups [15]) and in CSC's internal network firewall; different people inside CSC control both firewalls. The second HTTP proxy in cPouta is configured to only respond to queries from proxy number one in ePouta. This second proxy will relay the HTTP query to the Internet. Both proxies log all usage, and such usage can be reviewed afterwards in case the usage needs to be audited. A significant advantage of the proxy design is that access can be closed instantly in a few parts of the chain, in any of the proxies, or at the Cloud firewall level (OpenStack security groups). It is also possible to configure the setup to only allow (external) connections on a given schedule.

3.4 Administrator flow

The administrator flow is triggered only when a change is needed on any part of the system. This is the most powerful flow but also the most restricted one.

To log in to any of the Virtual Machines of both cPouta and ePouta, the administrator will need to use a private SSH key with access to the machines and on a computer connected to CSC's internal network, via a VPN or by being physically connected to CSC's office network.

To log in to any machine, it is necessary to first log in to the Virtual Machine JumpHost [16] in cPouta, the only machine with external SSH access. Then from the cPouta JumpHost, the connection is made into the Virtual Machine JumpHost in ePouta. And finally, from ePouta JumpHost into any Virtual Machines that form the HopsWorks cluster. The Virtual Machine JumpHost in cPouta is the only host that can connect to the corresponding JumpHost at ePouta. And in the same manner, only the Virtual Machine JumpHost in ePouta can connect to any other Virtual Machine in ePouta. This is enforced by firewalls in the OpenStack security group level and on the CSC's internal firewall level. As an additional security measure, no private key is stored in cPouta or ePouta. This means that if one of the hosts is compromised, no further access will be given to the attacker by the fact they control one of the hosts, because they lack the necessary secret key.

4 Technical security measures implemented for data security

This section will detail the technical security measures implemented for data security. This topic was discussed previously on D10.2 *Documentation of*

the secure data platform and its integration into HEAP. In this document, we discuss the final product and detail all the security measures and the security concerns they solve.

All data and processing compute resources are hosted in hardware in CSC's controlled data centers on Finnish soil. This means this solution adheres to Finnish requirements for sensitive data and complies with the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR). The services define the data processor (CSC) and data controller responsibilities. Researchers manage access to the data during all the phases of research and act as the Data Controller's representative, and they need to comply with CSC's general terms of use.

4.1 Data Transport Security Measures

The data is transmitted double-encrypted when in transit (between the researcher's computer and Allas).

The first encryption is the TLS encryption that HTTPs uses for client-to-server communication. The servers support only secure versions of TLS, this is 1.2 or 1.3 at this moment, following industry standards. These protocols will be removed if needed by new developments on data security standards, and at the same time, support for the latest versions will be added. For a correct and secure operation, HTTPs certificates have been deployed. These certificates are issued by universally recognised Certificate Authorities (CA) and are renewed so they always remain valid.

The second encryption layer is a strong Crypt4gh encryption applied to every file at origin. Before any data in a file leaves the researcher's computer, they are encrypted using Crypt4gh, which uses a public/private key model. This model is based on a publicly available public key, published online, that anyone can use to encrypt the data. Once encrypted, the data can only be decrypted by a private key on the secure ePouta servers hosting HopsWorks. The encryption is done on the user's browser by the SD Connect application. It is also possible to use the command line to make this process, by using the Crypt4gh encryption Utility [[17](#)] and an S3 or Swift compatible client like rclone [[18](#)], or s3cmd [[19](#)]. If the proper steps are followed, the final result will be the same, the data security will be preserved, and the same as using SD Connect.

The data will also be transported when it is needed for analysis. In this case, the connection is made between Allas (the server) and HopsWorks, which is installed in ePouta (the client). This operation uses several technologies. First, the data is transmitted using the S3 protocol over HTTPs using TLS 1.2 or better. It is a protocol created by Amazon for their service with the same name. Not only is the data transmitted via a secure channel, but it is also encrypted. This is similar to the previous scenario, where the files are

transmitted and double-encrypted. Once the files are in the Hopsworks cluster in ePouta, they must be presented to the researcher as unencrypted data. This is achieved by using a double FUSE layer, the first layer translates from the S3 protocol to a POSIX [12] file system view (the standard file view for UNIX systems). The second FUSE layer will take the POSIX file system view and present a decrypted file system view. Files are only copied on demand, i.e. when first accessed by the researcher, and are only kept in cache, never permanently written into the local disk of any Hopsworks host. Similarly, files are only decrypted when accessed, and the unencrypted file is only stored in memory, never on disk.

4.2 Data Store Security Measures

Files are always stored and encrypted using strong crypt4gh encryption, so no data is left unencrypted at rest. As mentioned, data is geographically located at CSC's data centres in Finland.

Data is stored in Allas object storage service. As mentioned, access to files stored in Allas (encrypted in this system) is managed by a pair of Access and Secret keys. These key pairs are only delivered to the system's administrators and the systems that need access, in this case, SD Connect and the Hopsworks ePouta cluster. Key pairs can be rescinded centrally from the Allas administration API if required.

Data stored in Allas is not being backed up, but it is stored in a redundant multiple-disk, multiple-server system. This means that it is improbable that data is lost or corrupted accidentally due to a system or hardware failure. However, there is no protection against accidental deletion by a system user with access to the files. If a file is deleted from the system by mistake by a system user, undeleting it is impossible. If a file is overwritten by mistake by a system user, restoring a previous copy of the file is impossible. These risks are mitigated by the Hopsworks system not having write or delete access permissions due to the conjugation of the aforementioned FUSE layers of file access.

4.3 Data Compute Security Measures

Computation is always performed on Virtual Machines located on ePouta, specifically on the Hopsworks cluster. The only available interface for researchers to access or use Hopsworks is via a web browser. No other access is possible. Web access uses HTTPs with TLS. Access via the web interface requires authentication, and it is necessary to possess a CSC account to authenticate.

All computation is performed on the Hopsworks cluster of Virtual Machines. Researchers can install and configure software to process the data already submitted to the cluster. Still, it is impossible for said processing software to connect to outside the Hopsworks cluster, or vice versa, the Hopsworks

cluster cannot be contacted from outside. It severely limits the possibilities of data being exfiltrated. The only way to export output data is by using the same process as the one used to import the original data, that is, via SD Connect. As an extra security measure, the data submitted via SD Connect is read only from inside the Hopsworks cluster, so output data needs to be written to a separate folder that will appear in SD Connect as an individual project.

4.4 Additional Security Measures

The Hopsworks cluster and its surrounding infrastructure are monitored for issues or unusual behaviour. This includes monitoring the Services for access, network and storage usage, and other measures to ensure service availability and security and to detect any unwanted or otherwise suspicious activity.

Security patches are being applied regularly, on a well-defined schedule. This is done so that the software is kept up to date with regular updates on all systems needed for the Cluster. Critical security patches are applied as soon as possible.

The personnel managing, administering, and developing the Services are being regularly trained for sensitive data processing according to general CSC training processes. This means that additional training, such as information security and privacy protection training, are being applied for the personnel responsible for the Services.

Administrative access to the Services is controlled and logged according to CSC administration guidelines and is limited to select CSC administrators. There is a separation of duties, e.g. service administration, network administration, and storage administration.

5 Summary

The main goal of this document is to describe the data security provided by the deployed platform. It achieves this by first defining the CSC services used by this platform. Secondly, by illustrating the integration between the different services, and providing a flow of the data and security measures. Finally, all the risks and measures are described.

6 References

1. CSC-IT Center for Science Ltd, Accessed March 2025, <https://csc.fi/>
2. CSC ePouta Virtual Private Cloud, Accessed March 2025, <https://research.csc.fi/service/epouta/>
3. Virtual machine flavors and Billing Unit rates, ePouta flavors, Accessed March 2025, <https://docs.csc.fi/cloud/pouta/vm-flavors-and-billing/#epouta-flavors>
4. OpenStack, <https://www.openstack.org/>
5. CSC Allas object storage service, <https://research.csc.fi/service/allas-data-storage-service-for-research-projects/>
6. Amazon Simple Storage Service S3, object storage protocol, Accessed March 2025, <https://docs.aws.amazon.com/AmazonS3/latest/API/Welcome.html>
7. OpenStack Swift object storage protocol, <https://wiki.openstack.org/wiki/Swift>
8. User documentation for CSC SD Connect, https://docs.csc.fi/data/sensitive-data/sd_connect/
9. CSC Allas object storage service documentation, Accessed March 2025, <https://docs.csc.fi/data/Allas/>
10. Crypt4gh, a secure method for sharing human genetic data, https://www.ga4gh.org/news_item/crypt4gh-a-secure-method-for-sharing-human-genetic-data/
11. Portable Operating System Interface, POSIX, Accessed March 2025, <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/POSIX>
12. Filesystem in Userspace, FUSE, Accessed March 2025, https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Filesystem_in_Userspace
13. Advanced Package Tool, APT, Accessed March 2025, [https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/APT_\(software\)](https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/APT_(software))
14. Package installer for Python, PIP, Accessed March 2025, [https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Pip_\(package_manager\)](https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Pip_(package_manager))
15. OpenStack security groups, Accessed 2025, <https://docs.openstack.org/nova/latest/user/security-groups.html>
16. Jump server, Accessed March 2025, https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Jump_server
17. Crypt4gh encryption utility, Accessed March 2025, <https://github.com/EGA-archive/crypt4gh>
18. Rclone, command-line program to manage files on cloud storage, Accessed March 2025, <https://rclone.org/>
19. s3cmd, tool for Amazon Simple Storage Service S3, Accessed March 2025, <https://github.com/s3tools/s3cmd>
20. HopsWorks is an enterprise-grade distributed AI Lakehouse platform, Accessed April 2025, <https://www.hopsworks.ai/>